

EDUCATION OF MORAL-VOLITIONAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL QUALITIES IN ATHLETES

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Annotation: The article reveals the features of the education of moral-volitional and psychological qualities in athletes. Sport is an excellent school for the development of volitional qualities in an athlete, which must be constantly carried out in the process of training sessions and competitions.

Key words: moral and volitional qualities, psychological qualities, athletes, sports, upbringing, education.

Introduction. Sport is an excellent school for cultivating volitional qualities in an athlete - purposefulness, determination and courage, perseverance and perseverance, endurance and self-control, initiative and independence, discipline [1, 2, 3]. Volitional qualities are brought up in sports wrestling, in the desire of an athlete to overcome his shortcomings, not be afraid of difficulties, to achieve a specific goal set for himself. These important qualities for an athlete are tested during sports competitions [4, 5, 6].

Purposefulness is expressed in the ability of an athlete to set specific goals for himself and strive to achieve them, in spite of any difficulties, subordinating all his thoughts, feelings and actions to the solution of the tasks set [7, 8, 9]. The goals that an athlete sets for himself are in accordance with the moral principles of a person. The decisiveness and courage of an athlete are manifested in the ability to independently and timely make well-considered decisions during a sports competition [10, 11]. Perseverance and perseverance are expressed in the ability of an athlete, regardless of difficulties, to achieve the goal, to actively fight for victory even in the most difficult, unfavorable conditions [12, 13, 14]. An athlete must have

willpower, the ability to overpower himself not only in training and competition, but also in everyday life.

Thus, willpower, perseverance and perseverance make it possible to successfully combine studies with sports, which requires a high personal organization from the athlete. An athlete needs to cultivate the quality of a winner in himself, to strive to be the first in big and small - in study, work, training, competitions [15, 16, 17].

Success in sports depends not only on the quality of training and physical activity, but also on the moral and volitional preparation of the athlete. One cannot be strong-willed and persistent in sports competitions and weak-willed, unprincipled in ordinary life [18, 19, 20]. It is not surprising that diligence is a particular manifestation of perseverance, because behind any high achievements of athletes there are years of hard work. To achieve a high goal, an athlete must also have self-control and self-control - the ability to control his thoughts, feelings and actions in any situation, especially in responsible competitions. These important qualities are manifested in his ability to control his behavior in any conditions, to manage his actions on the way to achieving a high result. Endurance and self-control, the ability not to get lost in difficult times, are important qualities possessed by the winners of sports competitions [21, 22].

In addition to the above-mentioned volitional qualities, in order to show stable high results in competitions, initiative and independence are of particular importance, i.e. the ability of an athlete to independently understand the current situation and act as necessary. These important qualities are expressed in the athlete's ability to independently set goals and outline ways to achieve them. Discipline, a quality inherent in almost all athletes - the ability to subordinate their actions, deeds to established rules and requirements of duty; It is expressed in the ability to consciously subordinate one's desires to the requirements of the collective, to put its interests above one's own interests.

Discipline is also manifested in strict observance of the sports regime, regular attendance at training sessions, firm fulfillment of the coach's tasks, but at the same time, the athlete must also be self-critical. Self-criticism and introspection is the ability of an athlete to analyze his actions and deeds depending on the intended tasks and conditions, the ability to see his mistakes and shortcomings and correct them, not to be conceited with success and not lose heart in case of failures.

Of course, one of the main conditions for the formation of volitional qualities is self-education. It is expressed in the athlete's desire to develop and improve the moral and volitional qualities of the individual [23, 24]. The direction of self-education is determined by the rules, principles that guide an athlete in everyday and sports life.

To improve the mental qualities of an athlete, one of the important areas is to reduce the level of emotional arousal in order to improve the overall balance of nervous processes and calm. In this case, the coach uses such techniques as verbal influence on the ward (clarification, persuasion, approval, praise), with the help of which the emotional tension of the athlete is reduced; his self-doubt, the excessive sense of responsibility for performance in the competition decreases [25].

The purpose of the training is to prepare for the highest sports achievements, which, as you know, depends on the sports capabilities and readiness of the athlete to achieve high sports results. With systematic training sessions in compliance with the methodical (didactic) principles of sports training, it is possible to achieve the necessary level of fitness, which allows an athlete to participate in competitions of various levels and show high sports results.

It has been proven by science and practice that sports capabilities are determined by the physical, technical and tactical abilities, as well as the special knowledge and competitive experience of the athlete. Readiness to achieve stable high sports results is characterized by the athlete's attitude to sports activities and the requirements of training and competition. Consequently, the preparation of athletes for sports achievements is a complex pedagogical process, which is divided into

education and upbringing. In the educational and training process, education and upbringing are inextricably linked. Therefore, the existing mutual connections between them should be used by the coach in order to increase the effectiveness of sports training.

At the same time, it is possible to single out the main components of the training process, which should be considered comprehensively:

1) physical training (the main content of which is the development of the athlete's physical abilities and his individual qualities);

2) technical training (its essence lies in the fact that the athlete has mastered the rational technique of the chosen sport, which will provide him with an economical and optimal use of physical qualities and abilities);

3) tactical training (its main content lies in the development of the athlete's ability to apply technical skills and abilities in certain situations of sports activities);

4) psychological preparation (an athlete must be able both in training and in competition to realize his physical abilities, technical skills, tactical concepts, despite the constantly increasing levels and density of results in rapidly changing conditions of sports activity);

5) education of personal qualities (in order to implement successful sports activities and achieve high sports results in competitions, an athlete must have a significant level of development of personal qualities).

Perseverance and perseverance in overcoming difficulties and achieving the goal is an important and integral part of the athlete's volitional training. During training sessions and competitions, athletes constantly have to overcome difficulties of a different nature - objective and subjective. As for almost all sports, this is, first of all, the fulfillment of a large training load, despite the growing fatigue, the painful experience of one's failures, and self-doubt when participating in competitions. Athletes have to constantly overcome these difficulties, which, of course, contributes to the development of strong-willed qualities.

In order for the athletes to be able to successfully overcome the listed difficulties during the competition, the coach must already during the training sessions put the athletes in conditions that are as close as possible to the competition; so training in cyclic sports takes place in any weather, the rest intervals between repetitions when lifting weights are reduced, the intensity of the load at the end of the lesson increases. Despite some uniformity of means and monotony of cyclical work during the movement in autumn and winter, a prerequisite for the development of strong-willed qualities is the complete fulfillment of the tasks planned by the coach.

Conclusions. An important role in the development of volitional qualities and in the preparation of an athlete as a whole is played by self-education and independence in training and participation in competitions, since excessive care on the part of the coach sometimes leads to negative phenomena in the preparation of athletes. Such an example can be the independent conduct of classes, which will largely contribute to the development of self-confidence in the athlete, will allow him to know himself, to identify (as a result of analysis) shortcomings, weaknesses in order to learn how to actively overcome them. As a rule, the high self-consciousness of athletes, their conviction, firm character sometimes have a decisive influence on the achievement of high sports results.

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